

Treatments and Interventions for Children with Autism

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The definition of autism has been changing over the past decades as a result of more studies done to better understand it. What remains unchanged about the disorder is the complexity of the condition and its causes cannot be fully determined. As a result, treatments and interventions for children with autism vary widely and cannot be a one-size-fits-all approach. This paper introduces readers to the different categories of treatments with examples of interventions for autism as well as to inform them of the need to check on credibility of such treatments and interventions that have claimed to help.

Defining Autism

The diagnostic criteria for autism (or autism spectrum disorder) have been changing over the past decades from the time when it was first coined by Bleuler (1911). However, our early understanding of autism comes from the pioneering works of Kanner (1943) and Asperger (1944).

With the publication of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) during the period 1980 to 2013, we have been provided a good grounding to understand what autism is and how its definition has been changing over that period. In a brief description, in DSM-III (APA, 1980), the onset of autism was placed prior to 30 months after birth with gross deficits in language development and pervasive lack of responsiveness to others. When DSM was revised and became DSM-III-R (APA, 1987), the onset of autism was put before 36 months of age with qualitative impairment in both verbal and non-verbal communication as well as in reciprocal social interaction. By the time DSM-IV (APA, 1994) was published and a further text revision was made when the manual was re-published as DSM-IV-TR (APA, 2000), a child is identified to have autism if he shows delays or abnormal functioning in one area (i.e., social interaction, language or play) before the age of 36 months with qualitative impairment in communication and social interaction. By the time DSM-V (APA, 2013) became available, a child has autism if he displays symptoms in the early developmental period (but these may not manifest until social demands exceed limited capacities, with persistent deficits in social communication and social interaction as well as deficits in social-emotional reciprocity and social relationships). According to Chia, Kee, Yusof and Lim (2015), “[H]yper- or hypo-sensitivity to sensory stimuli was included in DSM-III but was omitted in DSM-IV and DSM-IV-TR. Now, it has been included again in DSM-V” (p.80).

The Educator’s Diagnostic Manual (EDM) of Disabilities and Disorders (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2007) published by the American Academy of Special Educational Professionals uses the specific IDEA 2004 classification to define autism as “a developmental disability significantly affecting verbal and nonverbal communication and social interaction, usually evident before age 3 that adversely affects a child’s educational performance. Other characteristics often associated with autism are engagement in repetitive activities and stereotyped movements, resistance to environmental change or change in daily routines, and unusual responses to sensory experiences. The term does not apply if a child’s educational performance is adversely affected because the child has an emotional disturbance” [34 C.F.R. 3000.7(c)(1)]. In addition, EDM provides a comprehensive overview of the disorder under its code AU (Level I) and further identifies eight specific disorders for this classification (Level II): AU1.00 Asperger’s Syndrome, AU2.00 Autistic Disorder, AU3.00 Childhood Disintegrative Disorder, AU4.00 High-Functioning Autism, AU5.00 Hyperlexia, AU6.00 Multiplex Developmental Disorder, AU7.00 Rett Syndrome, and AU8.00 Other Types of Autism (to be designated specifically). EDM uses a five-level diagnostic coding system to help special educators understand how the disorder affects a child’s educational performance and how their IEP team can decide the extent to which the child needs support in terms of modifications, related services, assistive technology, classroom accommodations and a restrictive educational program outside the regular classroom.

In summary, autism is a complex developmental disorder that typically appears during the first three years of life. The disorder is best defined “by a certain set of behaviors and is a spectrum disorder that affects individuals differently and to varying degrees” (Autism Society of America, 2011, para.1). Hence, it is not possible to have a one-size-fits-all approach in terms of treatments and interventions for children with autism.

From Screening to Treatments and Interventions for Children with Autism

First a child suspected to have autism undergoes a three-level standard screening procedure (see Table 1) as proposed by Bishop, Luyster, Richler, & Lord, (2008). Level 1 is an initial screening procedure for all suspected cases, while Level 2 will focus on those with high probability of autism. Level 3 is a standard diagnosis to confirm if the child indeed has autism.

Once the child has been diagnosed with autism, the follow-up action is to seek an appropriate treatment that best meets his/her needs. The term *treatment* is used generally to cover medicine, pharmacology, psychology and education. Here, it refers to five broad categories as suggested by Simpson et al. (2005):

Table 1. Three-Level Screening Procedure for Autism.

Level 1 Screening Tests
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Checklist for Autism in Toddlers • Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers • Early Screening for Autistic Traits • Communication & Symbolic Behavior Scales – Developmental Profile • Pervasive Developmental Disorders Screening Test – Stage 1
Level 2 Screening Tests
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Communication Questionnaire • Screening Test for Autism in Two-Year-Olds • Childhood Autism Rating Scale • Gilliam Autism Rating Scale
Level 3 Diagnostic Tests
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autism Diagnostic Interview – Revised • Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule

1. Interpersonal relationship treatments;
2. Skill-based treatments;
3. Cognitive treatments;
4. Physiological/biological/neurological treatments; and
5. Other treatments and related agents that do not fall under one of the above four categories.

However, Cai et al. (2013) have replaced the fifth category with the interactive and digital media (IDM) based treatments to better represent the emerging research efforts using serious games, robotics and virtual reality technology. In this article, I have placed the IDM-based treatments as fifth category while pushing the fifth treatment category on Simpson et al.'s list to the sixth.

It is important to note the difference between treatments and interventions for children with autism although both terms seem to be the same. Unlike treatment, intervention “is a generic term used for any procedure or technique that is designed to interrupt, interfere with and/or modify an ongoing process” (Reber, Allen, & Reber, 2009, p.397). In medicine, intervention refers to particular surgical procedures (e.g., cystotomy) while in psychotherapy, it is to disrupt ongoing maladaptive behavior patterns (e.g., taking a child away from a dysfunctional family where he is being frequently abused). In special education, the goal of an intervention focuses on issues of cognitive and perceptual competence as well as the socio-emotional well-being of a child with special needs.

Table 2 shows examples of interventions under each of the six categories of treatments for autism.

Research-based Treatments and Interventions for Autism

Not all treatments and/or interventions are effective in treating or managing autism. It is better for us to caution the parents of children with autism, as well as the general public, not to believe everything found on the social or mass media about autism treatments and/or interventions. Simpson et al. (2005) have research-based evidence into four classes of treatments and interventions for autism: (1) practice that is scientifically based; (2) practice that is promising; (3) practice with limited supporting evidence; and

Table 2. List of Treatments and Interventions for Children with Autism.

Treatment Categories	Examples of Interventions
Interpersonal relationship treatments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Play-oriented strategies • Gentle teaching • Option method (Son-Rise Program) • Floor Time Plan • Pet/Animal assisted therapy • Relationship development intervention
Skill-based treatments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Picture Exchange Communication System (PECS) • Incidental teaching • Augmentative & alternative communication • Applied behavior analysis • Discrete trial teaching • Pivotal response training
Cognitive treatments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive behavioral modification • Cognitive learning strategies • Social stories • Cognitive scripts • Cartooning
Physiological/biological/neurological treatments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensory integration therapy • Auditory integration training • Megavitamin therapy
Interactive and digital media-based treatments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual reality-based therapies • Game-based learning • Robot dolls
Other treatments and related agents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art therapy • Music therapy • Gluten-free/casein-free diet

(4) practice that is not recommended. This classification system can serve as a check on different treatments and interventions for autism that have been promoted in the open market to ensure they are credible. Each level is briefly described below with selected examples.

Practice that is scientifically based: This first level refers to significantly rigorous research studies that have been carried out to demonstrate repeatedly and consistently similar results supporting the treatments and interventions for autism. Examples of scientifically based treatments include skill-based approaches, such as applied behavior analysis, discrete trial teaching and pivotal response training. Another example of scientifically supported cognitive treatment is the Learning Experience as Alternative Program for Preschoolers and Parents (LEAP).

Practice that is promising: This second level refers to treatments and interventions for autism “without any or with few adverse outcomes” (Simpson et al., 2005, p.11). They have been widely used for many years and individuals who have undergone these treatments and interventions show favorable responses. However, these treatments and interventions are still currently being studied to establish if they are truly scientifically based. There are many examples of such promising treatments. For example, in interpersonal relationship treatment, play-oriented strategies are a promising approach to socially engage children with autism, but such strategies must take into consideration these

children's socio-cultural contexts. Two examples of promising interventions in skill-based treatments are Treatment and Education of Autistic and related Communication handicapped Children (TEACCH), and Picture Exchange Communication System (PECS). Two examples of promising interventions in cognitive treatments include cognitive behavioral modification and social stories. Sensory integration therapy is one good example of a promising intervention in the physiological/biological/neurological treatments. In the IDM-based treatments, two promising interventions are virtual-reality based intervention programs and game-based learning. One example of the IDM-based treatment involves the virtual dolphin-assisted games (see Cai et al., 2013, for detail), for which I was a co-Principal Investigator in the pilot research project. According to several studies (e.g., Kee & Chia, 2010; Heiman et al., 1995; Nally, Houlton, & Ralph, 2000), children with autism possess strong visual modality that accounts for their fascination with and propensity for learning from videos and computer games delivered through electronic screen display. Fifteen participants with autism were involved in the pilot study. What we found out later from the study was that the participants' behavior, within the online virtual dolphinarium, was shaped by the dolphin avatar's visual characteristics and traits that are associated with specific behavioral stereotypes and expectations. This behavioral phenomenon is known as protean shaping, i.e., "[T]his change is due to the user's knowledge about the behaviors that other users, who are part of that virtual environment, typically associated with those characteristics" (Chia & Wong, 2015, p.7).

Practice with limited supporting evidence: At this third level, little or limited research has been done to study the efficacies of these treatments and interventions for autism. This category also includes those treatments and interventions whose results or outcomes range from poor to slightly (but not significantly) favorable. There are many such intervention programs across the six treatment categories. To name just a few here: option method (Son-Rise Program), pet/animal-assisted therapies, Fast ForWord program, cartooning, cognitive scripts, megavitamin therapy, Irlen lenses, art therapy, gluten-free/casein-free diet and music therapy. I had also conducted several studies (between 2007 and 2012) on the efficacy of dolphin-assisted therapy but findings remained inconclusive because it was difficult to determine the reliability and validity of findings based on anecdotal records (see Chia, Kee, & Chua, 2014, for detail). Yusof and Chia (2012) have cautioned that dolphin-assisted therapy serves best as a complement to other conventional therapies and should never be used as a sole treatment for children with autism.

Practice that is not recommended: This fourth level refers to treatments and interventions for autism that have undergone a substantial amount of rigorous research and the evidence shows a lack of favorable results, with serious detrimental effects and outcomes reported for those who have used them. Two good examples are holding therapy and the Facilitated Communication method.

The various treatments and interventions have been selectively chosen to illustrate my points in this article; the conclusions offered are based on my personal interpretation of the literature and my professional opinion. At the point of writing this article, research studies are still being conducted to evaluate the efficacy of each of these interventions.

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